

19. Uluslararası Dil, Edebiyat ve Kültür Araştırmaları Kongresi Tam Metinleri

Proceedings Book of The 19th International Congress on Language, Literature and Culture Research

كتاب المتون الكاملة للمؤتمر الدولي التاسع عشر للغات والآداب والدراسات الثقافية

Editörler - المحررون - Editors

Sami Baskın, Gehan M. Anwar Deeb, Muhammad Matarneh

04-08 Kasım/November 2025 - Antalya/Türkiye

ISBN: 978-625-92747-0-6

Yayımlanma Tarihi (Publishing Date): 30.11.2025

19. Uluslararası Dil, Edebiyat ve Kültür Araştırmaları Kongresi Tam Metinleri

كتاب المتون الكاملة للمؤتمر الدولي التاسع عشر للغات والآداب والدراسات الثقافية

Proceedings Book of The 19th International Congress on Language, Literature, and Culture Research

Editörler: *Sami Baskın, Gehan M. Anwar Deeb, Muhammad Matarneh*

Kapak Resmi:

KÜTÜPHANE BİLGİ KARTI

1. Basım, Elektronik Kitap (Çevrim içi / Web tabanlı)

210 x 297 mm

Kaynakça var, dizin yok.

ISBN 978-625-92747-0-6

1. Dil Bilimi 2. Edebiyat 3. Kültür Araştırmaları

PDF yayın

Yayımlanma adresi: <https://saybildercongress.com/dekak/>

Recent Academic Studies

Yeni Pazar Mh. Ali Okumuş Cad. Mevlana Sitesi A Blok – Çayeli / Rize

Kongre Onursal Başkanları - Honorary Presidents

Prof. Dr. İbrahim Özcoşar - Rector of Mardin Artuklu University, Türkiye
Prof. Dr. Mounir Dhouib - President of the Research Laboratory "GADEV/UMRAN" ENAU -
University of Carthage Tunisia

Düzenleme Kurulu / Organizing Board

Düzenleme Kurulu Başkanı - Head of the Organizing Board

Prof. Dr. Yakup Civelek – Ankara Hacı Bayram Veli University – Türkiye
Prof. Dr. Muhammad Matarna - Tafila Technical University - Jordan
Prof. Dr. Gehan M. Anwar Deeb - October 6 University - Egypt

Düzenleme Kurulu Üyeleri / Members of the Organizing Board

Prof. Dr. Hatem Fahad Hanoo - University of Mosul – Iraq
Prof. Dr. Muhammad Matarna - Tafila Technical University - Jordan
Prof. Dr. Najem Dhaher – Carthage University - Tunisia
Prof. Dr. Ömer Bozkurt - Mardin Artuklu University – Türkiye
Prof. Dr. Said Assil - Regional Center for Education and Training Professions – Morocco
Prof. Dr. Sami Baskın - Tokat Gaziosmanpaşa University - Türkiye
Prof. Dr. Sid Ahmed Sufyan - University of Annaba – Algeria
Prof. Dr. Gehan M. Anwar Deeb - October 6 University - Egypt
Dr. Esat Layek - Tokat Gaziosmanpaşa University - Türkiye
Dr. Yasser Ahmad – University of Bahrain – Bahrain

Üniversite Tarafından Bu Kongre İçin Görevlendirilmiş Düzenleme Kurulu Üyesi* Member of the Organizing Committee Appointed by the University for this Congress*

Prof. Dr. Ömer Bozkurt - Mardin Artuklu University - Türkiye

Değerlendirme Kurulu Başkanı – Head of The Evaluation Board

Prof. Dr. Gehan M. Anwar Deeb - October 6 University - Egypt

Değerlendirme Kurulu - Evaluation Board

- Prof. Dr. Abdel Basset Ahmed Marashdeh – Al al-Bayt University – Jordan
- Prof. Dr. Abdel Wahhab Al-Azdi – Mohammed V University, Rabat – Morocco
- Prof. Dr. Abdelhafid Bourdem – University of Maghnia, Tlemcen – Algeria
- Prof. Dr. Abdel-Rahim Azzam Marashdeh – Ajloun National University – Jordan
- Prof. Dr. Adnan Mahmoud Obeidat – University of Science and Technology – Jordan
- Prof. Dr. Amany Kamal – Ain Shams University – Egypt
- Prof. Dr. Amina Al-Yamlahi – Mohammed V University, Rabat – Morocco
- Prof. Dr. Awati Boubaker – Emir Abdelkader University of Islamic Sciences, Constantine – Algeria
- Prof. Dr. Azzedine Al-Zayati – Mohammed V University, Rabat – Morocco
- Prof. Dr. Ebtessam M. ElShokrofy – Damanhour University – Egypt
- Prof. Dr. El Mostafa Amrani – University of Sidi Mohamed Ben Abdullah, Fez – Morocco
- Prof. Dr. Gehan M. Anwar Deeb – October 6 University – Egypt
- Prof. Dr. Hanan Ahmed Selim – King Saud University – Saudi Arabia
- Prof. Dr. Hassan Ragab – Suez Canal University & Director of the Confucius Institute – Egypt
- Prof. Dr. Islam M. Abdel Salam – The Higher Institute of Specialized Studies – Egypt
- Prof. Dr. Janan Abdullah Younes – University of Mosul – Iraq
- Prof. Dr. Khaled Hadna – University of Mohamed Lamine Tanners, Setif 2 – Algeria
- Prof. Dr. Mohamed Ahmed Abu Nabout – Al Azhar University – Egypt
- Prof. Dr. Mohamed Ajmal – Jawaharlal Nehru University – India
- Prof. Dr. Mohamed Ben Zaoui – University of Brothers Mentouri Constantine – Algeria
- Prof. Dr. Mohamed Gaber ELMaghrabi – Alexandria University and Matrouh University – Egypt
- Prof. Dr. Mohammad Raghieb Deshmukh – S.G.B. Amravati University – India
- Prof. Dr. Muhammad Dawabsheh – Arab American University – Palestine
- Prof. Dr. Nehaa Abbas Aliwi – Al-Mustansiriya University, Baghdad – Iraq
- Prof. Dr. Nuh Doğan - Ondokuz Mayıs Üniversitesi – Türkiye
- Prof. Dr. Sahar Samir Yusuf – Al Azhar University – Egypt
- Prof. Dr. Said Assil – Regional Center for Education and Training Professions in Casablanca – Morocco
- Prof. Dr. Saida Kahil – University of Badji Mokhtar Annaba – Algeria
- Prof. Dr. Salah El-Din Zeral – University of Mohamed Lamine Tanners, Setif 2 – Algeria
- Prof. Dr. Sami Baskın - Tokat Gaziosmanpaşa University - Türkiye
- Prof. Dr. Sayed Sadik Al-Kady – Port Said University – Egypt
- Prof. Dr. Ubaidur Rahman – Jawaharlal Nehru University – India
- Prof. Dr. Yashodhara Pant – Tribhuvan University, Kathmandu – Nepal

Dr. Devkant Joshi – Principal of L.R.I. School in Kathmandu – Nepal

Dr. Doaa M. Anwar Deeb – Bayan House for Translation, Publishing & Distribution- Egypt

Dr. Enas Atwan Suleiman – University of Mosul – Iraq

Dr. Hassan Boudouh – Sultan Moulay Slimane University, Beni Mellal – Morocco

Dr. Mohamed Marzouk – Mohammed V University, Rabat – Morocco

Dr. Seyfullah Öztürk – Ondokuz Mayıs Üniversitesi – Türkiye

Dr. Yasser Ahmed Gomaa – Assiut University – Egypt

Sekreteryaya - Secretariat

Fırat Yılmaz

ÖN SÖZ

19. Uluslararası Dil, Edebiyat ve Kültür Araştırmaları Kongresi, 04–08 Kasım 2025 tarihleri arasında Türkiye'nin Antalya kentinde gerçekleştirilmiş; dil, edebiyat ve kültür alanlarını disiplinlerarası bir bakış açısıyla ele alan önemli bir bilimsel buluşma platformu olmuştur. Kongre, Saybiller Topluluğu organizasyonunda; başta Mardin Artuklu Üniversitesi (Türkiye) ve Carthage University (Tunus) olmak üzere çeşitli yükseköğretim kurumlarının akademik desteğiyle düzenlenmiştir.

Kongre kapsamında, farklı akademik gelenekleri ve araştırma perspektiflerini temsil eden 6 farklı ülkeden davetli konuşmacı bilim insanlarıyla buluşturulmuştur. Ayrıca Türkçe, İngilizce ve Arapça dillerinde yapılan çağrılarla geniş bir uluslararası katılım sağlanmıştır. Bu çok dilli ve kapsayıcı çağrı süreci sonucunda gönderilen bildiriler, bilimsel etik ve kalite ilkeleri doğrultusunda hakem değerlendirme sürecinden geçirilmiştir. Yapılan değerlendirmeler neticesinde Türkiye'den 34, Türkiye dışından ise Birleşik Arap Emirlikleri, Cezayir, Endonezya, Fas, Filistin, Irak, İran, Katar, Kuveyt, Mısır, Suriye, Suudi Arabistan Krallığı ve Ürdün olmak üzere 13 farklı ülkeden 114 bildiri, kongre programında yer almış; böylece toplam 148 bildiri bilim dünyasıyla paylaşılmıştır.

Bu kongre kitabında yer alan çalışmalar; dil, edebiyat ve kültür araştırmalarında güncel kuramsal yaklaşımları, özgün analizleri ve farklı coğrafyalardan gelen akademik deneyimleri bir araya getirmektedir. Kongre süreci, özellikle uluslararası ve kültürlerarası iş birliğine dayalı araştırmaların bilimsel bilginin evrenselleşmesi ve akademik etkileşimin sürdürülebilirliği açısından taşıdığı önemi bir kez daha ortaya koymuştur.

Bu bağlamda araştırmacıların; disiplinlerarası çalışmalara daha fazla yönelmeleri, ortak projeler ve çok yazarlı uluslararası yayınlar aracılığıyla akademik etkileşimi güçlendirmeleri ve farklı dillerde bilimsel üretim yaparak çalışmalarının görünürlüğünü artırmaları önem arz etmektedir. Üniversitelerin, araştırma merkezlerinin ve diğer paydaşların ise genç araştırmacıları destekleyen, uluslararası akademik ağları teşvik eden ve nitelikli bilimsel üretimi sürdürülebilir kılan yapılar oluşturmaya devam etmeleri gerekmektedir.

Bu kongrenin ve elinizdeki kitabın; alan yazınına anlamlı katkılar sunmasını, yeni akademik iş birliklerine zemin hazırlamasını ve dil, edebiyat ile kültür araştırmalarında nitelikli bilimsel üretimi teşvik etmesini temenni eder; kongrenin gerçekleştirilmesinde emeği geçen tüm kurumlara, hakemlere, davetli konuşmacılara ve değerli araştırmacılara teşekkür ederiz.

Prof. Dr. Gehan M. Anwar Deeb - October 6 University

Düzenleme Kurulu Başkanı

PREFACE

The 19th International Congress on Language, Literature, and Culture Research, held in Antalya, Türkiye, between November 4–8, 2025, constituted a significant academic platform that brought together studies in language, literature, and culture within an interdisciplinary framework. The congress was organized by the Saybilder Community, with the academic support of several higher education institutions, most notably Mardin Artuklu University and Carthage University.

Within the scope of the congress, invited speakers from six different countries met with scholars representing diverse academic traditions and research perspectives. In addition, calls for papers were announced in Turkish, English, and Arabic, enabling broad international participation. Following these multilingual calls, the submitted papers underwent a peer-review process conducted in accordance with scientific and ethical standards. As a result of the evaluations, a total of 148 papers were included in the scientific program, comprising 34 papers from Türkiye and 114 papers from 13 different countries, namely the United Arab Emirates, Algeria, Indonesia, Morocco, Palestine, Iraq, Iran, Qatar, Kuwait, Egypt, Syria, the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, and Jordan.

The studies presented in this proceedings book brought together contemporary theoretical approaches, original analyses, and diverse academic experiences from different geographical regions in the fields of language, literature, and culture. In particular, the congress clearly demonstrated the importance of international and intercultural collaborative research, emphasizing its crucial role in the universal dissemination of scientific knowledge and the establishment of sustainable interaction among different academic traditions.

In this context, researchers are encouraged to further engage in interdisciplinary studies, to strengthen academic interaction through joint projects and international co-authored publications, and to enhance the visibility of their research by producing scholarly work in multiple languages. Universities, research centers, and other stakeholders are likewise encouraged to continue supporting early-career researchers, fostering international academic networks, and developing sustainable structures for high-quality scientific production.

It is our sincere hope that this congress and the present proceedings book will contribute meaningfully to the existing literature, inspire new academic collaborations, and promote rigorous scientific research in the fields of language, literature, and cultural studies. We would like to express our gratitude to all institutions, reviewers, invited speakers, and distinguished researchers who contributed to the successful realization of this congress.

Prof. Dr. Gehan M. Anwar Deeb - October 6 University
Chair of the Organizing Committee

المقدمة

انعقد المؤتمر الدولي التاسع عشر للغة والأدب والدراسات الثقافية في مدينة أنطاليا - تركيا خلال الفترة من 4 إلى 8 نوفمبر 2025، وشكّل منصة علمية متميزة جمعت دراسات اللغة والأدب والثقافة في إطارٍ متعدد التخصصات. وقد نُظّم المؤتمر من قِبَل مجتمع سايبيلدر (Saybilder)، بدعمٍ علمي من عدد من مؤسسات التعليم العالي، وفي مقدمتها جامعة ماردين أرتقلو وجامعة قرطاج (Carthage University).

وشهد المؤتمر مشاركة متحدثين مدعويين من ست دول مختلفة، حيث التقى هؤلاء بنخبة من الباحثين الذين يمثلون مدارس أكاديمية ورؤى بحثية متنوعة. كما أُطلقت دعوات المشاركة باللغات التركية والإنجليزية والعربية، ما أسهم في تحقيق مشاركة دولية واسعة. وبعد ذلك، خضعت البحوث المقدّمة لعملية تحكيم علمي وفق المعايير الأكاديمية والأخلاقية المعتمدة. وأسفرت هذه العملية عن إدراج 148 بحثاً ضمن البرنامج العلمي، منها 34 بحثاً من تركيا و 114 بحثاً من 13 دولة هي: الإمارات العربية المتحدة، الجزائر، إندونيسيا، المغرب، فلسطين، العراق، إيران، قطر، الكويت، مصر، سوريا، المملكة العربية السعودية، والأردن.

وقد جمعت الدراسات الواردة في هذا الكتاب بين أحدث المقاربات النظرية، والتحليلات الأصيلة، والتجارب الأكاديمية المتنوعة من مختلف المناطق الجغرافية في مجالات اللغة والأدب والثقافة. كما أبرز المؤتمر بوضوح أهمية البحوث القائمة على التعاون الدولي والتفاعل الثقافي، لما لها من دور محوري في تعميم المعرفة العلمية وبناء تفاعل أكاديمي مستدام بين التقاليد العلمية المختلفة.

وانطلاقاً من نتائج هذا اللقاء العلمي، يُشجّع الباحثون على توسيع نطاق الدراسات البيئية، وتعزيز المشاريع المشتركة، والإسهام في النشر العلمي الدولي المشترك، إضافة إلى الإنتاج البحثي متعدد اللغات بما يزيد من انتشار الأبحاث وتأثيرها. كما تُدعى الجامعات ومراكز البحث وسائر الشركاء الأكاديميين إلى مواصلة دعم الباحثين الشباب، وتعزيز الشبكات العلمية الدولية، وبناء هياكل مستدامة تضمن جودة واستمرارية الإنتاج العلمي.

وإذ نأمل أن يكون هذا المؤتمر وهذا الكتاب قد أسهما في إثراء الأدبيات العلمية وفتح آفاق جديدة للتعاون الأكاديمي، فإننا نتقدم بخالص الشكر والتقدير إلى جميع المؤسسات المشاركة، والمحكمين، والمتحدثين المدعويين، والباحثين الكرام الذين أسهموا في إنجاح هذا الحدث العلمي.

رئيسة اللجنة التنظيمية

الأستاذة الدكتورة جيهان محمد أنور ديب

جامعة 6 أكتوبر

T.C.
MARDİN ARTUKLU ÜNİVERSİTESİ
Personel Daire Başkanlığı

Sayı : E-34233153-903.07-176180
Konu : Görevlendirme Hakkında (Prof.Dr.
Ömer BOZKURT)

25/12/2024

Sayın Prof.Dr. Ömer BOZKURT

Saybilder Congress Days kapsamında düzenlenecek olan aşağıda bilgileri belirtilen kongre/ sempozyumlarda Üniversitemizin sağladığı akademik destek kapsamında etkinliklerin düzenleme kurulunda bulunmak üzere Üniversitemizin akademisyen temsilcisi olarak görevlendirilmiş bulunmaktasınız.

Bilgilerini ve gereğini rica ederim.

19. Uluslararası Dil, Edebiyat ve Kültür Araştırmaları Kongresi (DEKAK):
<https://saybildercongress.com/>

19. Uluslararası Güncel Araştırmalarla Sosyal Bilimler Kongresi: <https://saybildercongress.com/>

19. Uluslararası Eğitim Camiası Sempozyumu: <https://saybildercongress.com/>

7. Uluslararası Sürdürülebilir Kalkınma ve Uzay Araştırmaları Kongresi:
<https://saybildercongress.com/>

7. Uluslararası İnsan, Toplum ve Sürdürülebilir Kalkınma Araştırmaları Sempozyumu:
<https://saybildercongress.com/>

Prof.Dr. Yılmaz DEMİRHAN
Rektör a.
Rektör Yardımcısı

Bu belge, güvenli elektronik imza ile imzalanmıştır.

İçindekiler - فهرس - Contents

Tragic Heroes in Modern Drama: John Proctor and Willy Loman – Exploring Ordinary Struggles in Modern Tragedy.....	1
Prof. Dr. Mohammad Abdullah Al Matarneh	
Yapay Zekâ Kullanımının Dilin Gelişimine ve Kullanımına Etkisi.....	9
Doç. Dr. Ali Yıldırım	
Sezai Karakoç'un Diriliş Düşüncesi ve Türkiye'deki İslâmî Oluşumlar Üzerindeki Tesiri.....	19
Dr. Öğr. Üyesi Şaban Banaz	
Yüksek Lisans Öğrencisi Bünyamin Gür	
Kıyamet Suresinde Belagat Göstergeleri ve Manaya Etkisi	36
Dr. Öğr. Üyesi Fikri Güney	
Postcolonial Nostalgia in Lahiri's <i>The Namesake</i>	46
Asst. Prof. Dr. Yıldray Çevik	
Genel Olarak Akşemsemeddin Divanı	53
Prof. Dr. Muhammed Ali Yıldız	
Türk Mitolojisinde Demire Dair Tespitler.....	59
Prof. Dr. Kadriye Türkan	
Yüksek Lisans Öğrencisi Metin Yaşa	

- Burdur Halk Kültüründe Unutulmaya Yüz Yüz Tutan Bir Gelenek: Duvak 64
Prof. Dr. Kadriye Türkan
- Erzurum'da Geçmişten Günümüze Ramazan Gelenekleri Üzerine..... 70
Yüksek Lisans Öğrencisi Betül Selimoğlu
- La profanation du sacré entre capitalisme culturel et redéfinition du sacré dans un cadre
postcolonial, étude de cas : « *The Holly Virgin Mary* » de Christ OFILI 80
Fatima Erramy
- 90 مقارنة مقارنة للمقطع الصوتي وبنية الاشتقاق في اللغات: الفارسية، العربية والعبرية.....
إلهام السوسي العبدلوي
- 104 حجة السلطة في الموازنة بين أبي تمام والبحتري للآمدي: مقارنة حجاجية في النقد العربي القديم.....
عبد المجيد الفروجي
د. سعيد أصيل
- 116 تمثيلات الجسد في المتن الصوفي بين التزكية الروحية والتعبير الرمزي.....
رشيد الحسيني
د. إلهام السوسي العبدلوي
د. عبد الرحيم الراشدي
- 129 القصيدة الإسلامية الخالدة (تأملات في نداء الأذان).....
د. عبد الرحيم الراشدي
- 137 الوجه في الدرس اللساني المعاصر مقارنة وظيفية للبنيات العلية في اللغة العربية.....
د. محمد نافع العشري

- 146 تأملات محمد الصباغ في الأدب: مصدر الأدب وطبيعته ووظيفته
د. المعتمد الخراز
- 170 توظيف التراث الديني والتاريخي في خطب أبي عبيدة الغزاوي
نجاهة البايي (الطالبة)
- 181 المرأة بين الجسد والرمز في الشعر العربي قراءة: مقارنة في الحب العذري والعشق الصوفي
الدكتورة طامو آيت مبارك
- 204 سلطة الشارح في التراث البلاغي: التفتازاني نموذجاً في ضوء نظريات التلقي الحديثة
إيمان البستاوي
- 214 أهمية الحفاظ على التراث الثقافي المغربي وآفاق تثمينه إعلامياً
دة بهيجة حيلات
- 224 المعمار اللغوي للشعر المملوكي (من الزخرفة إلى الرمزية)
الدكتورة ابتسام دهينة
بثينة ناجي (الباحثة)
- 232 ثلاثية أسفار مدينة الطين ما بين واقعية السرد والخيال (الميتا سرد منهجا)
د. عائشة بنت سالم سليمان العتيق
- 248 نظرية "محمد عنبر" اللسانية في "جدلية الحرف العربي" و"الشيء في ذاته"
الأستاذ الدكتور جمال مقابلة

253التخييل والإثنوغرافيا: أنياب طويلة في وجة المدينة" لمصطفى يعلى أنموذجا
الدكتور المصطفى فاتح

260حروف الجر في القرآن الكريم وإشكالية ترجمتها إلى اللغة الألمانية بالتطبيق على أمثلة مختارة
د. داليا إبراهيم نبهان

280تداخل الحقول المعرفية في قصيدة (بطاقة هوية) لمحمود درويش
د. أماني حافظ عبد الخالق الحفناوي

Challenges of Translating the Untranslatable Cultural Context and Colloquial Egyptian Arabic in
Mahmoud Diab's *The Stranger* 290

Prof. Dr. Gehan M. Anwar Deeb

Prof. Dr. Bahaa-eddin M. Mazid

In Pursuit of Life: A Realistic Portrayal of the Refugee's Dilemma in Omar El Akkad's *What Strange
Paradise*..... 301

Omnia Mostafa Niazy

Functional Study of the Arabic Translation of Samuel Taylor Coleridge's *The Rime of the Ancient
Mariner*: Artificial Intelligence Versus Human Intelligence in Literary Translation..... 313

Dina Ahmed Abdel Aziz Ramadan

Suspense Across Cultures: A Comparative Analysis of Selected Mark Twain and Nabil Farooq's Teen
Novels..... 325

Dr. Eisha AbdAllah Abdelkader Mohammed Askar

Minhaj al-Fiqh at-Tarjamī: Riddah against Western Control of The Qur'ānic Studies..... 343

Doaa Mohamed Anwer Deep

Language, Ritual, and Herbs: The Construction of Cultural Identity in Indonesian Traditional Medicine	365
Fika Hidayani, M. Hum Am'mar Abdullah Arfan, M.H.	
Physical Resilience in Words and Taste: A Sociolinguistic Analysis of the Spice Manuscript of the Indonesian Archipelago	379
Isriani Hardini, M.A., Ph.D. Prof. Dr. Zaenal Mustakim, M. Ag Dr. Rahmat Kamal, M.Pd.I.	
The Relationship between Language and Mental Processes and Language Processing Towards an Integrated Cognitive Framework for FLE Didactics	386
Dr. Khaoula Manaa	
Evaluative Scaling in Disaster Reporting: A Graduation-Based Analysis of English and Turkish News Texts	390
Asst. Prof. Dr. Hamide Çakır Sarı	
Turkish Films and Social Psychology: Socio-Psychological Presentation in <i>Gülen Adam</i> (1989)	412
Asst. Prof. Dr. Nurcan Bekil Çakmak	
Hurri-Hitit Mitindeki Sabotaj ve Direniş: <i>Ullikummi</i> Şarkısı Mitindeki İktidar, İsyân ve Kozmos	422
Dr. Öğr. Üyesi Z. Nihan Kırçıl	
Çağdaş Fonetik Araştırmaların Klasik Tecvid Birikimine Katkı Yönü	430
Dr. Öğreti Üyesi Mücella Hacımıroğlu	
"Sarraf" Kavram Alanı Ekseninde Türkçeden Diğer Dillere Geçen Sözcükler	439
Dr. Nihan Budak	

Bir Şairin Evlilikten Duyduğu Nedamet: Fahrî'nin "Kasîde Berâ-yı Nisvân" Adlı Manzumesi 464

Doç. Dr. Muhammet Nalbat

476.....العجائبية في رواية كويكول للكاتبه حنان لاشين
زوزو فيروز

Exploring the Ecological Discourse of Dark Ecology as a Radical Form of Posthumanism493

Asst. Lect. Mustafa Arkan Khntel

502.....من ألفاظ المعجم الفلاحي المزاي دراسة مقارنة بالمعجم العربي
د. عبد الوهاب بافلح

517.....الأبعاد التداولية في معجم الدوحة التاريخي للغة العربية
دكتور مصطفى أصلان

531.....أثر التوجيه النقدي في تطور الإبداع الأدبي العربي
الأستاذة دربالي وهيبه

546.....تحولات الشخصية ودورها في تشكيل العالم الروائي: دراسة سردية لرواية "مملكة الفراشة" لواسيني الأعرج
د. ليلى حمراي
نجاه بشير

563.....توظيف المنهج التقابلي في تعليم النحو العربي للناطقين بالتركية
د. نادر مندريس

574.....دور الترجمة في نقل المعنى بين العوالم
بشرى الكاضي

- 580..... المرأة الفلسطينية في رواية التفاصيل والأشياء: رواية سروال بلقيس نموذجاً
د. فاطمة حسين عيسى العفيف
- 594..... اللغة العربية بين التأليف والانسلاخ
الدكتورة سعاد اليوسفي
- 603..... التواصل بين الثقافات: النظم اللغوية وسلوك التغيير: مفاتيح لاكتساب وتطور اللغتين الأمازيغية والغوارانية
بابا محمد
- Said Nursî'de Aşk ve Şefkat Kavramlarının Mukayesesi..... 616
Yüksek Lisans Öğrencisi Yücel Özdiğer
Prof. Dr. Muhammed Ali Yıldız
- 622..... أدب الرحلات، قراءة في كتاب (مغامر عماني في أدغال أفريقيا)
أ.د. عبد الباسط أحمد مراشدة
- 628..... الاستلزام الحوارى في قصيدة بشارة الخورى عش أنت إنى مت بعدك
أ. ولاء إبراهيم الشبول
- 637..... الرّمكان الشّعريّ للصورة البصريّة عند ابن زمرك
الأستاذ المشارك أحمد عمر
- 650..... البشاعة الاستطيقية في قصيدة "المخبر" لبدر شاكر السياب: قراءة في جماليات القبح وفضح السلطة
د. أسعد اللايق
- 661..... صورة القبيح في شعر نزار قبّاني: الشعوب المستلبة أنموذجاً
أ.م. د. عبد الحليم عبد الله

- Child Labor Trafficking in Frances Temple's *Taste of Salt: A Story of Modern Haiti* 672
Assistant Instructor Asmaa Mohanad Saad
- The Uses of Translation Techniques to Achieve an Appropriate Translation 681
Dr. Osama Misbah Mahmood Al-Hamdani
- Gendered Asymmetries in Terms of Address in Moroccan Arabic 688
Yassine Akhmouch
- Restless Female Characters in Edwidge Danticat's *Breath, Eyes, Memory* 697
Assist. Lecturer Mashail Faris Saleh
- 704.....ترجمة المصطلحات المرتبطة بالأنظمة الأنجلوسكسونية من الإنجليزية إلى العربية.....
فيروز بورمة
- 711.....التمثيل السيميائي للأنوثة في رواية "امرأة سريعة العطب" لواسيني الأعرج: أنوثة على حافة الانكسار، من العنوان إلى الذات
المتشظية.....
د. ليلى حمراي
نجاه بشير
- 722.....الأبعاد النفسية في المجموعة القصصية (الفخ) دراسة في ضوء المنهج النقدي النفسي -.....
م.م. أنسام أركان حريز
- 733.....سيميائية الموت والحياة في الشعر الفلسطيني الحديث (تميم البرغوثي أنموذجاً).....
أ.م.د. جيدم فاروق عبد الحكيم
- 741.....حقيقة التناوب في الاستعمال بين " على " و"حروف الجر الأخرى في القرآن الكريم - دراسة تحليلية.....
م. د. باسم محمد صالح جمعة الجبوري

- 752.....التوكيد في آية الكرسي دراسة نحوية دلالية.....
الدكتور أحمد طالب محمد الياسري
- 760.....دلالة ألفاظ الفناء في الحكم العطائية.....
م.م. آية عبد العزيز محمد أمين
أ.م.د. محمد محمود سعيد
- 769.....الدُّر المنثور في بلاغة التشبيه القرآني.....
المدرس الدكتور أنوار جاسم عويد
- 779.....التمرد في رواية شرف للكاتب صنع الله إبراهيم.....
مدرس مساعد نور عادل محمد حميد
- 789.....الحزن وبواعثه في الشعر النسوي العراقي الحديث "دراسة موضوعية".....
أ.م.د. فائق غانم النعيمي
- 798.....تأثير الرواية العرفانية في تشكيل الوعي الأخلاقي رواية "المر: أختام المدينة الفاضلة" لعبد الإله بن عرفة أنموذجا.....
د. للا الهاشمية باباهاشم
- 806.....الأفيون والذاكرة للروائي يحيى بزغود: قراءة سوسولوجية تاريخية.....
د. حسناء بزغود
- 815.....تفاعل اللغة والمجتمع، التنوع اللغوي والتأثير الاجتماعي في اللغة: مقارنة لسانية وصفية.....
اسليماني رضوان

La profanation du sacré entre capitalisme culturel et redéfinition du sacré dans un cadre postcolonial, étude de cas : « The Holly Virgin Mary » de Christ OFILI 826

Fatima Erramy

Dr. Nabil Benabdeljalil

Physical Resilience in Words and Taste: A Sociolinguistic Analysis of the Spice Manuscript of the Indonesian Archipelago

Isriani Hardini, M.A., Ph.D.

Universitas Islam Negeri K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid, Pekalongan, Indonesia

Prof. Dr. Zaenal Mustakim, M. Ag

Universitas Islam Negeri K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid, Pekalongan, Indonesia

Dr. Rahmat Kamal, M.Pd.I.

Universitas Islam Negeri K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid, Pekalongan, Indonesia

Abstract

Traditional medicine in Indonesia functions as a significant cultural system for understanding health and bodily balance. This study analyzes the Tetamba manuscript from Cirebon, West Java, a historical text compiling medicinal recipes using spices from the Indonesian archipelago. While previous research has primarily treated such manuscripts as historical or ethnobotanical records, this study addresses the lack of exploration regarding their linguistic and symbolic dimensions. The objective is to examine how physical resilience is linguistically constructed and semiotically encoded through words and sensory metaphors, and how language functions to transmit medical knowledge across generations. Methodologically, this study employs a qualitative descriptive design utilizing sociolinguistic and semiotic approaches, incorporating frameworks by Hymes, Halliday, Peirce, and Barthes. Data were collected through textual documentation and close reading to identify lexicon and expression patterns related to healing. The findings indicate that the Tetamba manuscript fulfills a dual function: it serves as both a practical medical guide and a cultural text encoding values of protection and endurance. Physical resilience is constructed through lexical choices and metaphors connecting the body to nature, where sensory descriptions of taste and heat symbolize vitality and balance. Furthermore, the text's instructional language legitimizes healing authority, ensuring the preservation of traditional wisdom. Ultimately, the manuscript provides historical evidence of how the concept of bodily resilience was shaped through the interconnection of words, taste, and social practice.

Keywords: Tetamba manuscript, traditional medicine, physical resilience, sociolinguistics, semiotics

Introduction

Since ancient times, traditional medicine has been a well-established component of Indonesian culture, playing a significant role in the nation's healthcare landscape. The practice of combining and consuming herbal remedies has its origins in the Majapahit Kingdom era, as evidenced by the Madhawapura Inscription. The use of traditional medicines in Indonesia has been documented in various written sources dating back hundreds of years (Sukini, 2018). This suggests that medical knowledge was not only transmitted orally but also recorded meticulously, emphasising the importance of documentation in the transmission of medical knowledge. As the historical records illustrate, traditional medicine functioned as a cultural system that shaped collective understandings of health, endurance, and bodily balance.

A significant written document that records this tradition is *Tetamba*, a historical manuscript that provides detailed information about traditional medicine. The *Tetamba* manuscript is written in Javanese Cirebon and Arabic, using both *Pegon* and *Arabic* scripts, reflecting the interaction between local knowledge and Islamic scholarly traditions. The total thickness of the manuscript is 177 pages, and it presents a comprehensive overview of herbal ingredients, preparation methods, and healing concepts (Hidayani, 2023). Beyond its medical content, *Tetamba* can be regarded as a cultural artefact in which language plays a pivotal role in the structuring and legitimisation of traditional medical knowledge

Despite the richness of such manuscripts, a significant problem remains in current research: traditional medicinal texts are often treated merely as historical or ethnobotanical sources. Concurrently, the linguistic and symbolic dimensions of the phenomenon have received only marginal attention. In particular, there is a lack of research on how language in these manuscripts constructs the concept of physical resilience and how specific lexical choices, metaphors, and sensory expressions function within the broader cultural system. Therefore, the communicative and ideological functions of language in traditional medicine have not been adequately explored.

Previous studies in the field of sociolinguistics have emphasised that language functions as a reflection of cultural identity and social practice, providing a crucial foundation for analysing physical resilience as a culturally constructed concept. Hymes (1974) and Halliday (1978) conceptualise language as a social semiotic system through which communities articulate experiences of the body, health, and endurance within specific cultural contexts. This perspective is further supported by Fishman's (1972) concept of language as a medium for intergenerational transmission of knowledge and Bernstein's (1971) theory of linguistic codes, which provides a detailed explanation of how authority and access to traditional knowledge are regulated. In the Indonesian context, studies by Rahmawati (2020) demonstrate that health-related narratives and metaphors encode social roles, power relations, and moral values associated with bodily resilience. However, the majority of studies in this field have focused on oral traditions, thus leaving the linguistic construction of physical resilience in written spice and medical manuscripts insufficiently explored.

From a semiotic perspective, the foundational theories of Peirce (1931) and Barthes (1972) offer analytical tools with which to understand how words and expressions of the senses operate as signs that produce cultural meaning. Recent studies on the subjects of food, taste, and medicine demonstrate that sensory terms such as bitter, warm, and spicy symbolise balance, vitality, and

strength Leong (2015) and Wierzbicka (2018) . In Indonesia, Yuliana's (2021) analysis of *Serat Centhini* reveals how metaphors of taste and the body articulate moral discipline and physical endurance in traditional manuscripts. Nevertheless, these studies tend to prioritise symbolic interpretation over sociolinguistic function, resulting in limited insight into how words and taste jointly function as communicative resources for transmitting concepts of physical resilience in spice manuscripts of the Indonesian Archipelago.

This research aims to examine how the concept of physical resilience is linguistically constructed and semiotically encoded in the *Tetamba* manuscript. The study focuses on the use of words, phrases, and sensory metaphors related to taste, heat, and bodily conditions, while also analysing how language functions as a medium for transmitting traditional medical knowledge across generations. By situating the manuscript within its socio-cultural and historical context, the research highlights the role of language as both a symbolic system and a communicative practice.

Following the stated aim, the study aims to address two primary research questions. The following questions are investigated: firstly, how is the concept of physical resilience constructed in the text through the use of words and phrases? Secondly, how does language function as a medium for transmitting traditional medical knowledge across generations? The following questions guide the analysis by combining sociolinguistic and semiotic approaches to capture both social meaning and symbolic representation in the manuscript.

The originality of this study lies in its interdisciplinary framework and its focus on *Tetamba* as a relatively understudied traditional medical manuscript. The integration of sociolinguistic theories (Hymes, Halliday, Fishman, Bernstein) with semiotic theories (Peirce, Barthes) contributes to a more comprehensive understanding of the linguistic structuring of traditional medical knowledge, its cultural preservation, and its symbolic transmission. The study positions *Tetamba* not only as a historical medical document but also as a linguistic and semiotic artefact that symbolises Indonesia's cultural philosophy of physical resilience and continuity.

Methodology

The study uses a qualitative descriptive research design, using sociolinguistic and semiotic approaches to analyse the linguistic construction of physical resilience in the Spice Manuscript of the Indonesian Archipelago. A qualitative approach is considered appropriate in this instance, as it enables in-depth interpretation of the cultural meanings embedded in historical texts (Creswell, 2012). The primary data source consists of selected textual excerpts from the Spice Manuscript, including words, phrases, and sentences related to medicinal recipes, herbal practices, and health concepts. As a text-based study, the 'participants' are not human subjects but linguistic units within the manuscript that represent voices of traditional healers and cultural knowledge systems. Secondary data include previous sociolinguistic, semiotic, and ethnobotanical studies, which function as theoretical support and interpretative triangulation.

Data were collected using textual documentation and close reading techniques. The data collection process followed Hymes' (1974) framework for ethnography of communication was used, with the manuscript being thoroughly read in order to identify linguistic patterns associated with resilience and healing. Cultural significance was attributed to selected examples containing metaphors and sensory

references (e.g., taste, heat, and aroma), and the data were systematically coded. The linguistic units were then categorised into three primary groups. The following elements are to be considered:

(a) lexical indicators of physical resilience,

(b) metaphorical and sensory expressions, and

(c) language of transmission and instruction. In order to ensure that linguistic forms were interpreted within their socio-cultural environment, contextual elements, including communicative purpose, implied participants, and cultural setting, were also noted.

The integration of data analysis with sociolinguistic interpretation and semiotic analysis was undertaken to achieve a comprehensive understanding of meaning. The sociolinguistic analysis was informed by Hymes' speaking model and Halliday's systemic functional linguistics to examine the ideational, interpersonal, and textual meanings in healing discourse. The analysis was informed by semiotics, with the semiotics model of Peirce (1931) being utilised, along with Barthes' (1972) theory of myth and connotation, and Lotman's (1990) cultural semiotics. These theoretical frameworks were employed to interpret the function of words, tastes, and medicinal symbols within a broader semiosphere of cultural meaning. Ethical considerations centred on cultural sensitivity, respect for indigenous knowledge, and proper acknowledgement of the manuscript as cultural heritage. The primary constraint of this study is its reliance on textual data, which precludes direct observation of contemporary practices or oral interpretations. However, this limitation is addressed by rigorous theoretical triangulation and contextual analysis.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the main findings of the study on how the concept of physical resilience is constructed and interpreted through language and taste in the Spice Manuscript of the Indonesian Archipelago. The analysis focuses on lexical patterns, metaphors, and sensory expressions, such as taste, heat, and aroma, that function as linguistic and symbolic media in representing physical resilience and transmitting traditional medicinal knowledge. By integrating sociolinguistic and semiotic approaches, this discussion not only describes the linguistic forms that appear in the text, but also interprets their social, cultural, and ideological functions, thereby positioning the spice manuscript as a linguistic artifact that reflects the relationship between language, culture, and physical resilience in Indonesian medicinal traditions.

A. Linguistic Construction of Physical Resilience

Analysis of the Spice Manuscript of the Indonesian Archipelago reveals that the concept of physical resilience is constructed through recurring lexical choices, metaphors, and culturally embedded expressions related to the body, strength, and natural balance. Moreover, metaphorical phrases, such as "the body as a vessel of fire and earth" or "the blood flows with spice" (as translated from old Javanese and Malay sources), highlight how the text constructs resilience through analogies between natural elements and human vitality. Following Lakoff and Johnson's (1980) concept of conceptual metaphor, these linguistic images link physical health with ecological balance, implying that resilience is sustained through harmony between the body and the natural world.

From Hymes' (1974) ethnography of communication lens, these expressions are more than descriptive; they function as culturally meaningful speech acts within healing rituals or oral storytelling. Words

about strength and recovery are performed in social contexts that reinforce communal identity and shared belief systems.

The use of vocabulary, sentence structure, and language style in the *Tetamba* manuscript serves more than just as a practical guide to the use of spices. This manuscript also reflects cultural values regarding resilience, protection, and physical treatment. Here is the example of the sentences in Javanese in the *Tetamba* manuscript.

Punika tatamba awak panas, saranane godong widasari lan ades palasari lan kelapa pinanggung maka pinipis kabeh den lembut maka binorehaken ing larane. Insya Allah waras ilahi.

Translation:

This is a treatment for body heat. It uses three ingredients: widarasari leaves, palasari fennel, and coconut. First, the ingredients are roasted over a fire until they are boiling. Then, they are pounded and applied to the sick body. Inshallah, this treatment heals for Allah's sake (Page 5).

From the sociolinguistic perspective, this study found some adjectives in Javanese such as *awak panas* (body heat), *waras* (healthy) functions as what Halliday (1978) calls ideational meanings language that represents the speaker's experience of the world. These terms reflect how physical resilience is socially valued within the community's worldview, particularly in relation to endurance against illness and environmental hardship.

B. Language as a Medium for Transmitting Traditional Medical Knowledge

The Spice Manuscript also demonstrates how language serves as a cultural and intergenerational bridge for transmitting traditional medical wisdom. Through Halliday's interpersonal and textual metafunctions, the manuscript positions the healer as a knowledgeable authority and the listener or reader as a cultural apprentice. Recurrent patterns such as directive verbs (use, boil, mix, pray) and imperative structures reflect the instructional nature of the text.

This aligns with Sillitoe's (1998) argument that indigenous languages encode ecological and medicinal expertise within their lexicons. Similarly, Nabhan (2004) emphasizes that oral and written linguistic traditions are key to the survival of ethnobotanical knowledge. In the Spice Manuscript, linguistic repetition, especially in ritual formulas and parallel constructions, ensures memorability, aiding the oral transmission of healing recipes and practices.

Furthermore, from a cultural semiotic perspective, the manuscript functions as part of Lotman's (1990) semiosphere, where words and sensory experiences (taste, aroma, heat) coexist as interrelated signs. Spices such as ginger, turmeric, clove, and nutmeg operate as both physical and semiotic elements: they have tangible healing properties and symbolic meanings associated with protection, endurance, and vitality.

In Peirce's (1931) semiotic model, these spices act as objects, their linguistic representations (representamens) evoke interpretants, understandings of health and resilience within the cultural system. The repeated association of heat and strength, for example, signifies the community's belief that warmth restores balance and prevents disease, a concept that bridges linguistic, medical, and cosmological knowledge.

C. Cultural Symbolism of Taste and Resilience

Taste descriptions, such as *pedas* (spicy), *hangat* (warm), and *pahit* (bitter), play a significant semiotic role in encoding values of physical and moral strength. Following Barthes (1972) taste operates as a mythic code, where food and medicine are not merely functional but carry ideological meanings. “Spice” becomes a cultural symbol of resistance, both against illness and external environmental pressures.

Lotman’s (1990) cultural semiotics helps interpret these sensory representations as texts within the broader cultural semiosphere. The act of consuming spice-based medicine symbolizes not only bodily restoration but also participation in a shared cultural narrative of resilience. Thus, the Spice Manuscript embodies a semiotic dialogue between the tangible (taste, ingredients) and the intangible (beliefs, cultural identity).

D. Negotiating Physical Resilience through Language and Symbolism

The findings demonstrate that the Spice Manuscript is not merely a record of herbal remedies but a semiotic and sociolinguistic artifact that encodes the community’s philosophy of resilience. Through language, the manuscript transforms physical experience into cultural meaning, bridging the biological, ecological, and spiritual dimensions of health.

By integrating Hymes’ ethnography of communication and Halliday’s systemic functional linguistics with Peirce’s and Lotman’s semiotic models, this study shows that resilience in the Spice Manuscript is both linguistically constructed and symbolically perpetuated. The manuscript serves as a site of meaning negotiation, where traditional medical knowledge is preserved not only through content but also through linguistic style, metaphor, and sensory association.

Furthermore, the negotiation of physical resilience within the Spice Manuscript reflects a dynamic process of knowledge regulation and cultural continuity. Linguistic choices related to taste, heat, and bodily sensation function not only as descriptive elements but also as symbolic markers that legitimize healing authority and guide interpretive understanding among community members. These sensory-linguistic patterns enable resilience to be communicated as an experiential and moral concept, rather than a purely physiological condition. Consequently, the manuscript operates as a cultural interface where language mediates between embodied experience and collective ideology, ensuring that traditional medical knowledge remains intelligible, authoritative, and meaningful across generations.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The conclusions of this study indicate that the Tetamba manuscript fulfils a dual function, serving not only as a practical guide for the utilisation of spices in traditional medicine, but also as a cultural text that encodes the community's understanding of physical resilience. The vocabulary, sentence structure, and stylistic features found in the manuscript reflect deeply rooted values related to protection, endurance, and bodily care. The manuscript reveals how the people of the Indonesian Archipelago conceptualised resilience as a holistic condition encompassing physical, cultural, and symbolic dimensions, as demonstrated through the interconnection of words, taste, and social

practice. Consequently, Tetamba is significant as both a medical reference and a historical record of how language mediates the construction of bodily resilience within traditional knowledge systems.

In accordance with these findings, it is recommended that future research be conducted in the form of interdisciplinary studies integrating linguistics, semiotics, and health studies. Such studies could lead to the expansion of comparative analyses across regions and manuscripts, thus facilitating a more profound comprehension of the diversity of resilience concepts in Indonesian cultural heritage. Furthermore, analysis of the Tetamba manuscript may inform contemporary efforts to revitalise local knowledge as part of sustainable and culturally founded health systems, thus ensuring that traditional wisdom is preserved, contextualised, and conscientiously integrated into modern health practices.

References

- Barthes, R. (1972). *Mythologies*. Hill and Wang.
- Bernstein, B. (1971). *Class, Codes and Control*: Routledge.
- Creswell, J. W. (2012). *Research Design Pendekatan Kualitatif, Kuantitatif, dan Mixed*. Pustaka Pelajar.
- Fishman, J. A. (1972). *The Sociology of Language: An Interdisciplinary Social Science Approach to Language in Society*. Rowley, Newbury House.
- Halliday, M. A. K. (1978). *Language as Social Semiotic: The Social Interpretation of Language and Meaning*. Edward Arnold.
- Hidayani, F. (2023). Ramuan Tradisional Nusantara Abad Ke-16 Naskah Tetamba Cirebon. *Tamaddun*, 11(2), 68–107.
- Hymes, D. (1974). *Foundations in Sociolinguistics: An Ethnographic Approach*. University of Pennsylvania Press.
- Leong, E. (2015). Recipes and Remedies: The Semiotics of Medicine in Early Southeast Asia. Singapore. *Journal of Humanities*, 12(2), 87–103.
- Lotman, Y. M. (1990). *Universe of the Mind: A Semiotic Theory of Culture*. Indiana University Press.
- Peirce, C. S. (1931). *Collected Papers of Charles Sanders Peirce*. Cambridge.
- Rahmawati, N. (2020). Health and Resilience in Javanese Proverbs: A Linguistic Study. Indonesian. *Journal of Language and Culture*, 8(1), 55–70.
- Sillitoe, P. (1998). The development of indigenous knowledge: A new applied anthropology. *Current Anthropology*, 39(2), 223–252. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1086/204722>
- Sukini. (2018). *Jamu Gendong Solusi Sehat Tanpa Obat*. Badan Pengembangan dan Pembinaan Bahasa.
- Wierzbicka, A. (. (2018). *Language and Cultural Scripts: Understanding Taste and Emotion across Cultures*. Oxford University Press.
- Yuliana, D. (2021). Food, Body, and Morality in Serat Centhini: A Semiotic Perspective. *Jurnal Budaya Nusantara*, 9(1), 45–60.

يمثل هذا الكتاب الإصدار العلمي الرسمي للمؤتمر الدولي التاسع عشر لبحوث اللغة والأدب والثقافة، الذي عُقد في أنطاليا - تركيا خلال الفترة من 4 إلى 8 نوفمبر 2025، بتنظيم من جمعية سايبيلدر وبالشراكة مع عدد من الجامعات والمؤسسات الأكاديمية في تركيا وتونس ودول أخرى. ويضم هذا العمل مجموعة منتقاة من الأبحاث المحكمة التي اجتازت مراحل المراجعة العلمية وفق معايير الجودة والأمانة الأكاديمية.

تعكس الدراسات الواردة في هذا المجلد التنوع المعرفي والغنى المنهجي في مجالات اللغة والأدب والثقافة، كما تبرز قيمة التعاون العلمي الدولي من خلال مشاركة باحثين من ثلاث عشرة دولة. ويؤكد هذا الإصدار أهمية دعم الحراك البحثي متعدد التخصصات وتشجيع الإنتاج العلمي بلغات مختلفة بما يعزز حضور المعرفة في فضاء البحث العالمي.

وإذ نقدّم هذا الكتاب إلى المجتمع الأكاديمي، نعبّر عن تقديرنا للجهات الداعمة والهيئات العلمية والمحكمين والباحثين المشاركين، آمليين أن يسهم هذا العمل في تعزيز الدراسات ذات الصلة وفتح آفاق جديدة للتعاون الأكاديمي المستدام.

ISBN: 978-625-92747-0-6

